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Updated Report on Dissemination, Community Building, Collaborations, Training, and Exploitation Plans

WP6: Dissemination, Community Building, Training and Exploitation

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Authors	David Tskhakaya (IPP CAS), Ales Podolnik (IPP CAS) and Jeremy Williams (KTH)
Responsible Author	David Tskhakaya (IPP CAS) E-mail: tskhakaya@ipp.cas.cz
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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we discuss the background, methodology and outcomes of project dissemination; present lists of the manuscripts published, or accepted for publication at scientific journals in 2024 and of the international conferences, where we had invited, oral and poster contributions in 2024. We discuss the efforts made for community building, new collaborations and training sessions, which took place under the Plasma-PEPSC project during 2024. These demonstrates that dissemination, community Building, collaborations, training, and exploitation activities performed agree to project initial plans.

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1 Introduction

The aim of the activities in WP6 is to perform wide dissemination of the project outputs and achievements; to plan and contribute to the community building within and outside the project; strengthen existing and establish new collaborations in the research field as well as with other CoEs (Centers of Excellence) and NCC (National Computer Centers); to support organization of project meetings and training sessions. Special efforts to be directed towards increasing of user pools of the software developed under this project, as well as optimization of the high-level support of such community.

The main aim of the dissemination activities is to disseminate project outcomes and maximize their impact. In these activities project members follow the main principles: awareness creation in the general public and decision makers, promotion of developed codes and other software to professional communities, knowledge transfer. Correspondingly, dissemination activities are divided according to the target communities; e.g. for general public the main dissemination tools represent press releases, popular lectures, website, YouTube webinars, LinkedIn and Twitter/X account of the project. Dissemination to the plasma and HPC communities and industry is done mainly via contributions to scientific conferences, meetings and journal publications. These activities are supported by different code training sessions and by continuously nearing newly developed code access to the open-source software standards.

2 Dissemination

2.1 Website

The Plasma-PEPSC's [website](#) contains general information, important contacts, announcements and useful code repository information. The website has been updated continuously to include additional material and content. The number of site visitors in 2024 till November 30th was 1771 (increased more than 40% against 2023), see Fig. 1. The Plasma-PEPSC project is also presented on our industry partner, SiPearl, [website](#) in the “European projects” section.

2.2 Twitter/X

Plasma-PEPSC's [Twitter/X account](#) continues to play a large part in the project's dissemination strategy. The account has been used by researchers to promote events and disseminate talks they have given, or participated in, as well as news from the HPC community (see Fig. 2). Twitter has been an easy way of reaching out to the public by using a platform people trust and works side by side with the Twitter/X's website. At present it has more than 1500 followers and its popularity increased significantly (in January 2024 there were only 20 followers).

Figure 1: Geography of Plasma-PEPSC website visitors in November.

Figure 2: Plasma-PEPSC Twitter/X page.

Figure 3: Plasma-PEPSC LinkedIn page.

Figure 4: One of the Plasma-PEPSC YouTube webinars.

2.3 LinkedIn and YouTube Webinars

The Plasma-PEPSC's [LinkedIn account](#) is utilized in 2024. It contributes significantly to the dissemination of the project outcomes: at present it has more than 90 followers (see Fig. 3).

In 2024 we continue dissemination activities through [YouTube webinars](#). at present (December 2024) we have already recorded 10 webinars (see Fig. 4), for comparison, in 2023 we had only 1.

Figure 5: At the Baltic HPC and Cloud Conference in Riga.

2.4 Scientific Publications

In 2024 Plasma-PEPSC has published nine open-access papers that are available online and are listed on the project's website: ([4], [1], [9], [7], [6], [8], [5], [2], [3])

2.5 Conference contributions

The outputs of Plasma-PEPSC project have been presented at different HPC and application-oriented conferences, as invited, oral presentation and poster contributions (see the list below and Fig. 5)

- PASC 2024, Frontier Exascale HPC, AI, Workflows, Zurich, Switzerland, 3 - 5.6.2024 <https://pasc24.pasc-conference.org/>
- EuroHPC Summit 2024, Antwerp, Belgium, 18-21.03.2024 <https://www.eurohpcsummit.eu/>
- Baltic HPC and Cloud Conference, Riga, Latvia, 11-12.04.2024 <https://encs.se/events/4th-baltic-hpc-and-cloud-conference/>
- Europar 2024, PHYSHPC, Madrid, Spain, 27.8.2024 <https://physhpc.github.io/>
- MNHACK24, 6th MareNostrum Hackathon, Barcelona, Spain, 7 - 9.10.2024 <https://www.bsc.es/es/news/events/mnhack24-6th-marenostrum-hackathon>
- Alpaka and openPMD Workshop and Hackathon, Dresden, Germany, 23-25.10.2024 <https://events.hifis.net/event/1657/>
- The International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage, and Analysis, Atlanta, USA, 17-22.11.2024 <https://sc24.supercomputing.org/>

Figure 6: SiPearl posters at the ISC in Hamburg and Supercomputing in Atlanta.

Our industry partner, SiPearl contributed to 6 high performance, quantum computing and AI dedicated conferences and forums. SiPearl posters (see Fig. 6), press kits (see Fig. 7) and booklets distributed at these conferences include sections dedicated to the Plasma-PEPSC project.

- ISC High Performance 2024, Hamburg, Germany, May 12-16, 2024 <https://www.r-ccs.riken.jp/en/outreach/events/20240512-16/>
- Vivatech, Paris, France, May 22-25, 2024 <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/events/vivatech/>
- Teratec, Paris, France, May 29-30, 2024 https://teratec.eu/gb/forum_2024/workshops.html
- France Digitale Day, Paris, France, September 18, 2024 <https://fdday.eu/>
- Supercomputing in Atlanta, Atlanta, USA, November 18-21, 2024 <https://www.openmp.org/events/sc24/>

3 Collaboration with other CoEs

We continue collaboration with our partner CoEs, [Castiel 2](#) and [SPACE EuroHPC](#); the Plasma-PEPSC members are actively engaged in online and face-to-face meetings and trainings (e.g. [see here](#)); providing input and feedback to the Castiel 2 deliverables. We established collaborations with other CoE, [EXCELLERAT](#) and organized a common [Digital Twins meeting](#).

We also collaborate with EuroHPC initiatives, pilot systems and different NCCs: [EPI](#), [EUPILOT](#), [EUPEX](#) and [the German NCC](#).

SiPearl involved in core European projects to ensure sovereignty

Cloud	Centres of Excellence
<p>AERO</p> <p>Developing an open-source software ecosystem needed to optimize the efficiency of EPI hardware and facilitate the integration of SiPearl's microprocessors in the cloud.</p>	<p>EXCELLERAT P2</p> <p>Making some of the most used HPC application suites in engineering and manufacturing work on exascale EuroHPC supercomputers based on SiPearl's microprocessors.</p>
<p>Riser</p> <p>Developing the 1st all-European RISC-V cloud server infrastructure, significantly enhancing Europe's open strategic autonomy.</p>	<p>MAX DRIVING THE EXASCALE TRANSITION</p> <p>Developing materials modelling, simulations and discovery technologies, and making them accessible to a vast community of researchers.</p>
<p>OpenCUBE</p> <p>Developing a custom cloud installation with the guarantee that an entirely European solution can be deployed reproducibly.</p>	<p>PLASMA PEPSC</p> <p>Promoting scientific and technological progress in key areas such as magnetic confinement fusion, industrial plasmas, medical applications...</p>

And also regional projects:
Emopass (France), FlexFMM (Germany)

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Figure 7: Page 28 of the SiPearl's press kit given during ISC, Vivatech, Teratec, France Digitale and Supercomputing trade-shows.

Important to point our collaboration with the industry, namely with fusion related organizations, [Novatron Fusion](#) and [Proxima Fusion](#), as well as space companies [Aurora Propulsion](#), [Finnish power grid](#) and [Leonardo](#).

4 Community Building

As part of our community-building initiatives, Plasma-PEPSC coordinated a [CoE/ENCCS hybrid workshop](#), Stockholm, Sweden, 13-15.2.2024; participated at the [all-Hands Meeting](#) (NCC/CoE Meeting) in Vysoké Tatry, Slovakia, 21-24.04.2024, co organized a meeting - [Digital Twins for Future Fusion Reactors](#), Ljubljana, Slovenia, 25-26.9.2024, and finally, organized two general Plasma-PEPSC meetings in Barcelona (10-11.4.2024) and Garching (15-17.10.2024), see Fig. 8.

We had more than 20 online Plasma-PEPSC Executive and more than 40 Work Package meetings in 2024.

5 Training

Plasma-PEPSC training activities were performed at dedicated hybrid training (see below) and co-organized meetings (see 2.5, 4). They aimed to provide participants with an understanding of Particle-in-Cell (PIC) codes and their exascale capabilities, explain high performance I/O libraries (openPMD, ADIOS-N), logging practices, performance measurement, code testing features, and perform demonstrative simulations.

In addition, we continued series of Webinar showcasing important technologies and software developed in the project (see 2.3).

Figure 8: Face-to-face meeting in Barcelona.

6 Exploitation

The Plasma-PEPSC code owners, including IPP CAS with BIT, MPG with GENE, HZDR with PIconGPU, and UoH with Vlasiator, are committed to leveraging the significant advancements achieved by Plasma-PEPSC in terms of performance and portability. This effort aims to enhance community adoption and foster collaborations with European agencies, initiatives such as EURATOM, EuroFusion, and ESA, as well as various national and international research communities. The Exploitation of project outcomes is done through industry, academic, and research centers.

An inventory of companies and startups connected to Plasma-PEPSC partners who are potentially interested in adopting Plasma-PEPSC codes includes companies mentioned in 3. We especially note SIPEARL, which being a member of the project, represents a primary industrial partner for Plasma-PEPSC playing a pivotal role in advancing the EU's strategy for improved autonomy and sovereignty in High-Performance Computing (HPC). Collaboration involves working closely with SIPEARL processors and state-of-the-art accelerators within the project time-frame.

Academic partners, including KTH, TUM, UoH, and UL, will focus on exploiting their contributions through academic channels such as seminars and courses based on their work. Additionally, they aim to expand their network between industry and academia in Europe, engage in research projects to facilitate technology transfer to European industries and SMEs, and contribute to standardization bodies such as MPI.

HPC and Research Centers (MPG, BSC, FORTH, HZDR, and IPP CAS) will strategically address plasma simulation optimizations crucial for their HPC system users. The anticipated scientific publications resulting from their research endeavors will not only improve their academic standing but also initiate new collaborations.

7 Conclusion

Our WP6 activities in 2024 can be summarized as follows. We reached all milestones for this year; namely, we were actively disseminating project outputs in social media: project website, Twitter/X; generated LinkedIn account and were updating our YouTube channel. We participated in 14 international conferences and meetings on HP computing, with more than 16 contributions; organized face-to-face and hybrid Code Camps for code owners and user training; published 9 papers. We plan to have a press release in December.

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